

ECONOMICS

NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC'S IMPACT ON TOURISM THROUGH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF TRANSIT TRANSPORTATION AND LOGISTICS OPERATIONS

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Abstract

The Zangazur corridor, which will unite the entire Turkic world, will become a corridor connecting Asia with Europe. After the realization of this strategic project, Azerbaijan will significantly contribute to the implementation of regional connectivity projects such as the East-West, North-South, and North-West transportation corridors.

The creation of the Zangazur corridor will also end the blockade of Nakhchivan, turning the autonomous republic into a logistics hub. Establishing a land connection with the main part of Azerbaijan will boost Nakhchivan's economic development, stimulate investment in the region, lead to the creation of new production facilities, and open up additional job opportunities. The opening of this transportation corridor will enhance Nakhchivan's role as a transit transportation and logistics center. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic will become one of the developed tourism regions in the country and the region as a whole.

Keywords: Nakhchivan, Zangazur corridor, transportation, logistics, tourism, transit.

INTRODUCTION

The development of a country's transport and logistics system, the presence of many alternatives for foreign and domestic transportation are important for the economic development of this country and the safe implementation of import and export operations. Azerbaijan stands out as a regional logistics and transit center with its geographical position, strategic transit points and developed transport infrastructure. The historical Silk Road passing through Azerbaijan shows that our country has ancient traditions in the field of logistics. Our country has become a transport hub with its location at the intersection of energy and trade routes and developed infrastructure. Azerbaijan, which is an important link in the restoration of the Ancient Silk Road, also acts as the initiator and implementer of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, "North-South", "East-West" International Transport Corridors. Besides playing the role of a gateway between East and West, our country is also an important transit center connecting North and South. All this indicates that our country has a strategic position [2].

The Zangezur corridor, which will connect the entire Turkic world, will also be the corridor connecting Asia and Europe. After the implementation of this strategic project, Azerbaijan will make an important contribution to the implementation of regional connectivity projects such as East-West, North-South, North-West transport corridors. The project will reshape the transportation map not only of this region, but of the world as a whole. One of the important strategic importance of the Zangezur corridor is the symbolic connection of East and West Zangezur.

A declaration was signed between Azerbaijan, Russia and Armenia, which includes the victory of Azerbaijan. This clause of the agreement will stimulate the restoration of transport and communication links in the region and the strengthening of Azerbaijan's position in the international transport and logistics system.

The statement also included a provision on the restoration of economic and transport relations with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Until the November 10 agreement, the direct transport connection between other regions of Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan was possible only through air routes, and opening this transport corridor will create an opportunity for the construction of alternative road and railway lines that can bring cheaper and more export-import volume to an expensive means of transport. With this, Nakhchivan will become the main artery of the regional transport system.

EXPLANATION OF THE PROBLEM

Due to the lack of land connections, Nakhchivan was excluded from all regional and international transit projects in which Azerbaijan participated. This led to the Autonomous Republic not being able to benefit from these projects and being economically blocked. During the economic blockade, the solution was to provide connections by air transport and crossing the territory of third countries, which required additional time and cost. By ensuring land connections with Nakhchivan, Nakhchivan MR will be able to connect to the transport network in other regions of Azerbaijan and export its products to other regions of Azerbaijan, as well as to Europe and Asia with more convenient opportunities. With the diversification of the transport and communication system in the post-blockade period, Nakhchivan will accelerate its economic development, save costs for imports, increase the volume of exports, and attract foreign investment to the economic region by being recognized in large markets [7].

Another existing problem in the development of multilateral economic relations between Asia and Europe on the international scale will be solved with the restoration of land connections. Nakhchivan will play the role of a bridge between the Caspian Sea and the Mediterranean Sea by building these transit lines and will provide safe, cheap and fast transportation for the countries on the Silk Road. In addition, Nakhchivan

will be in a key position in the transportation of international goods to Europe through the integration into the "North-South" transport corridor and the planned Kars-Igdir-Nakhchivan railway lines.

At the same time, with the end of the blockade, the relations of Nakhchivan with other regions of Azerbaijan will be further strengthened. This means the development of tourism in Nakhchivan and the increase in the number of domestic and international tourists.

THE TRANSFORMATION OF NAKHCHIVAN INTO A TRANSPORT-LOGISTICS CENTER AND ITS INTEGRATION INTO INTERNATIONAL TOURISM

As we know, after the forced annexation of Zangezur to Armenia in 1920, Nakhchivan was blockaded and forced to live isolated from the main part of Azerbaijan. The creation of the Zangezur corridor will not only remove Nakhchivan from the blockade. After the opening of this transport corridor, the autonomous republic will become a logistics center. Providing a land connection with the main part of Azerbaijan will boost the economic development of Nakhchivan, stimulate investment in the region, create new production enterprises, and create additional jobs.

The establishment of a transport communication system with Nakhchivan is also of great importance in terms of distance and, consequently, the speed of cargo delivery. In the future, the road lines that will pass through the territory of Nakhchivan will reduce the cost and duration of transportation by being 1.7 times the length of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line, approximately 343 kilometers less, and the Nakhchivan transport hub will be complementary to the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line, making it the center of Central Asia and Europe. will act as a bridge between Also, as the driving distance to Turkey via Nakhchivan will be approximately 343 kilometers shorter, the two-way movement of tourists between the two countries is expected to increase the entry into the country from the territory of Nakhchivan [3].

Economic relations between Nakhchivan and other regions of the country, which do not have land routes, created additional time and costs. After the restoration of the Nakhchivan-Land road, it is predicted that this number will increase further as tourists who want to go to other regions of Azerbaijan will also use this road. The expansion of entry into the country through Nakhchivan will indirectly have a positive effect on the development of tourism in Nakhchivan.

By connecting to the planned Kars-Igdir-Nakhchivan railway lines with the restoration of the road, it will be easier to transport international goods to Europe from Azerbaijan to Turkey. As a result, the transportation costs of the products exported from Azerbaijan will decrease, and trade relations with the whole of Turkey, especially the Eastern Anatolia region of Turkey, including the cities of Ağrı, Ardahan, İğdir and Kars, as an international logistics hub of Nakhchivan, will expand further. New priorities will have a positive effect on the development of friendly and brotherly relations between the states of Azerbaijan and Turkey based on new perspectives, on the realization of newer projects, on the further strengthening of the territorial integrity of our country, and on the further increase of

the mega-economic importance of the projects of our republic. will realize tourism mobility at the level of tets [2].

In recent years, many works have been carried out in Nakhchivan in order to turn Nakhchivan into an international transport and logistics center and to carry out many operations in this area.

In the past 20 years, the reconstruction of the Nakhchivan-Sadarak, Nakhchivan-Julfa, Julfa-Ordubad highways, the preservation of the railway, the repair of the railway stations, the creation of the International Airport, and the modernization of the transport infrastructure as a whole are among the measures calculated for today's era.

Creation of 3, 4 and 5-star hotels, modern shopping centers, and restaurant chains in the autonomous republic is one of the factors that will ensure the transformation of Nakhchivan into an international transport and logistics center.

In modern times, the development of information and communication technologies at the required level is one of the main issues in order for any region to become a logistics center. Currently, the activity of mobile operators in our country has been ensured in the territory of Nakhchivan, and the autonomous republic's own mobile operator Naxtel has been established. In June 2005, Nakhchivan was able to connect to the Trans-Asia-Europe fiber-optic main line to ensure a faster flow of information, and access to the Internet was improved in the autonomous republic.

Gas stations on the side of highways from Sadarak to Ordubad, underground and surface parking lots, and car repair centers have been put into use in Nakhchivan. They will provide 24-hour service to drivers of trucks and cars that will use Nakhchivan as transit [8].

In order for Nakhchivan to function as an international transport and logistics center, a modern customs system should be in place. This is because customs bodies have important responsibilities in ensuring and facilitating the continuity of international trade. Taking into account international standards and local conditions, customs complexes, customs laboratory built for Julfa in 2007, Shahtakht in 2009, and Nakhchivan City Customs in 2012, administrative building commissioned for Nakhchivan Air Transport Customs Department in 2014, the new administrative building and warehouse complex built and put into use for "Nakhchivanterminalcomplex" Union in 2015 meets the highest standards.

After the opening of the Zangezur corridor, all the necessary measures have been taken in advance to turn the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic into a transport and logistics center. However, there is still work to be done. For example, in the cities of Sharur, Julfa and Ordubad, there will be a serious need for at least hostel-type accommodation in the future. In addition, it is advisable to build small cafes and restaurants on the sides of the main road from Sadarak to Ordubada.

Very minor deficiencies will be resolved before the opening of the Zangezur corridor. And in the near future, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic will become not only the developed region of our country, but also the region as a whole, the transport and logistics center.

Conclusion

By ensuring land connections with Nakhchivan, Nakhchivan MR will be able to connect to the transport network in other regions of Azerbaijan and export its products to other regions of Azerbaijan, as well as to Europe and Asia with more convenient opportunities. With the diversification of the transport and communication system in the post-blockade period, Nakhchivan will accelerate its economic development, save costs for imports, increase the volume of exports, and attract foreign investment to the economic region by being recognized in large markets.

The main benefit of the transport corridor in tourism is the transportation benefit. Therefore, this road will be very important in the field of both cargo and passenger transportation. Traveling from our capital and other areas to Nakhchivan MR will be done both cheaply and in a short time frame. With this, the number of domestic tourists coming to Nakhchivan will increase. At the same time, there will be an increase in the number of people going on tourism trips from Nakhchivan to Baku and other regions of Azerbaijan.

At the same time, the Zangezur Corridor will play a major role in expanding the relations of Azerbaijan to Europe through Turkey, to Asia through Iran, and to Russia through Baku. With this, in the future, both socio-economic relations and tourism relations will expand further in the region. The opening of the corridor with Nakhchivan also means the possibility of establishing Russia's relations with Turkey, as well as Russia's relations with Iran, actually through Azerbaijan. This is an issue that serves intensive development of tourism in the region as a whole. The expansion of relations will also be manifested in the field of tourism. The number of tourists coming to Nakhchivan from Turkey and Russia will increase [6].

By connecting to the planned Kars-Igdir-Nakhchivan railway lines with the restoration of the road, it will be easier to transport international goods to Eu-

rope from Azerbaijan to Turkey. As a result, the transportation costs of the products exported from Azerbaijan will be reduced, and trade relations with the whole of Turkey, especially the Eastern Anatolia region of Turkey, including the cities of Ağrı, Ardahan, Iğdir and Kars, as an international logistics hub of Nakhchivan, will expand further [3].

As it can be seen, the Zangezur Corridor is of great economic importance and has a positive effect on the development of Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur economic regions, as well as the development of Nakhchivan, which is an integral part of Azerbaijan, and integration into the economy of the region where our country is located, including Asia and Europe able to accelerate.

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